

Editorial

Surfaces—Our First 100 Papers

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Surfaces (ISSN 2571-9637; CODEN: SURFCY) is a peer-reviewed open access journal covering all aspects of surface and interface science, and it is published online quarterly by MDPI. Its mission is disseminating rigorously peer-reviewed and high-quality scientific contributions.

The inaugural Editorial was given to the Scientific Community on 30th March 2018 (<https://www.mdpi.com/2571-9637/1/1/1>) and Volume 1 was distributed on December 2018. We have just delivered issue 4 of Volume 3, reaching the relevant milestone of paper no. 100. We are proud of this achievement and want to thank all scholars that contributed to such a success.

So far, the published papers have already accumulated 254+ citations overall, 97,000+ abstract views on the journal website, and 113,000+ downloads. I think that we have achieved what we promised in the inaugural Editorial where we said that we wanted to make “*Surfaces* a recognized forum for the exchange of the newest advancements of Surface Science”.

The community of scholars that is actively contributing to the development of *Surfaces* is now composed of 4 Editors and 44 Members of the Editorial Board (<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/surfaces/editors>) and I take this occasion to strongly acknowledge their substantial role. We really welcome any other scholar willing to contribute to this joint venture.

At the very beginning, in the inaugural Editorial, we emphasized “the term interdisciplinary, and not multidisciplinary, because one of the goals was to break boundaries among different disciplines, harmonizing them into a coordinated and coherent whole”. Even this goal has been more than achieved. Actually, the papers so far published are spreading into several topics and disciplines, namely Chemistry, Physics, Catalysis, Materials Science & Engineering, Nanoscience, Biointerfaces and interfacial phenomena in Biology and Nanomedicine, targeting applications in many very strategic fields such as sensors, energy conversion and storage, environmental and food science, and medical devices.

Now, the journal is under evaluation by Web of Science for the coverage of ESCI or SCIE. We look forward to keep receiving your contributions to *Surfaces* and to expand the actual indexing of the journal.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

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